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ABSTRACT

This report describes the test stands constructed at CERN and the IAP at Goethe University Frankfurt with its different configurations and unique diagnostics as well as the first performance tests of the IRME-gun that has been developed within the scope of ARIES.

ARIES Consortium, 2022

For more information on ARIES, its partners and contributors please see <http://aries.web.cern.ch>

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Executive summary

First, the two different test stands located at CERN and the IAP at Goethe University Frankfurt are described, which were constructed to test the RF modulated electron gun developed within the scope of ARIES WP16 (IRME). Next, the development process of the IRME electron gun and its power modulator is briefly summarized. Finally, the first performance tests of the IRME-gun at the E-lens laboratory in Frankfurt are reported. Full performance of the IRME-gun could not yet be demonstrated as the project was severely impacted by restrictions at the partner institutes and supply difficulties during the COVID-19 pandemic. Tests will continue after the end of ARIES.

1. Introduction

ARIES work package 16 is a Joint Research Activity (JRA) project aimed at the creation of intense RF-modulated electron (IRME) beams for application in electron lenses for space charge compensation. Accordingly, an RF-modulated electron gun that delivers electron currents of up to 10A with modulation frequencies between 0.4 and 1 MHz was designed, constructed and tested. After manufacturing the gun performance was examined at the test stand at the IAP (Institute for Applied Physics) of Goethe University Frankfurt.

Initially it was planned to perform the final gun tests at the electron lens test stand at CERN which was designed to meet all requirements of the IRME-gun. Nevertheless, a modification in the project strategy was necessary because of the COVID-19 pandemic. All partners were forced to adapt their schedules and resources for risk minimization and to avoid unnecessary travel of staff. Exchange of hardware was also made difficult because of safety regulations. The operation of the IRME-gun requires the use of a dedicated high-voltage terminal, for which adaptation of the CERN test stand and approval from the CERN safety officer would have been necessary. Moreover, the operation and experiments with the RF-modulated electron beam need on-site presence of the developer of the electron gun and the power modulator, conditions that were impossible to meet because of travel restrictions during the Covid crisis. In addition to this, several experimental tests had to be performed during the iterative design and construction process of the gun at Goethe University Frankfurt. Under these circumstances, it was decided mid of 2020 in agreement with the ARIES project management to perform the gun tests at a test stand to be constructed at IAP in parallel to the test stand at CERN and provide virtual laboratory access to this test stand for the leader of task 16.4 and the collaborators of WP16.

Following this decision, at IAP a dedicated laboratory (E-Lens Lab) was provided and equipped with a high voltage platform to power the electron gun. Two solenoids were delivered by GSI to operate the electron gun and to transport the beam to the beam dump. A water-cooled beam dump for a power deposition of 27 kW was available at IAP, which can also be used for time-resolved beam diagnostic. In summary, all hardware components needed for beam production and transport experiments were already at hand.

While these fortunate circumstances allowed switching the location for the gun tests during the time span of the ARIES project, the important amount of work required for the construction of the new test stand and the continuation of the COVID crisis beyond 2020 made that it was not possible to make up for all the delays incurred due to the COVID-19 regulations and to the complex construction of the second test stand. The preparation of the infrastructure of the new E-Lens Lab but especially the installation of a high-voltage terminal to power the gun, which has to be operated by a dedicated control system, required considerable efforts. In addition to this, within the final phase of the project some technical set-backs were experienced concerning the cooling system of the gun. This made the exchange of insulator parts and the optimization of the cooling circuit necessary; to power the gun on the high voltage platform an adaption of the cooling system was required. During an initial test, the cooling circuit of the plasma chamber which hosts the arc discharge to heat the cathode was plugged due to impurities of the cooling water. Although the system was operated at low power the critical temperature was reached and as a result the insulators were damaged. Meanwhile, the cooling circuit was optimized and the tests of the terminal are ongoing. Although all components were tested and preparation for beam tests completed, it was not possible to fully demonstrate beam extraction from the electron gun until the end of the ARIES project.

Nevertheless, it must be emphasized, that an additional test stand at IAP besides the one previously constructed at CERN offers additional benefits for the accelerator community that were not foreseen in the original planning. In particular, the second test stand increases the test capabilities for the development of electron guns for e-lenses, for which many applications are discussed presently in the accelerator community. Thus, it enables the possibility to develop electron guns for different e-lenses in parallel.

This report presents the different test stand set-ups at CERN and IAP. It then gives a summary of the design and construction process of the IRME electron gun and its modulator, providing the results of experimental tests at intermediate steps. Finally, the report presents the results of the first performance tests the RF-modulated electron gun obtained at the IAP test stand.

2. E-Lens Test Stand at CERN

2.1 GOALS AND MOTIVATION

2.1.1 Hollow Electron Lens

Due to the high stored energy in the HL-LHC beam tails (estimated to be in the order of 30 MJ above 3 beam σ with beam emittance of $2.5 \cdot 10^{-6}$ rad m [1]), it is desirable to have active halo control providing more margin during all the operational phases of HL-LHC.

Hollow Electron Lenses [2], [3], give a mean of depleting the tails without using intercepting material, avoiding the risk of damage and not contributing to machine impedance. Halo particles that migrate into the electric field generated by a hollow electron column travelling concentrically around the circulating proton beam over a short distance, will be ‘kicked’ to larger oscillation amplitudes (a slow, continuous process) and be pushed towards the collimators. This leads to a cleaning of the tails.

At CERN, Hollow Electron Lenses [4], [5] for HL-LHC are planned to be installed, one per beam line (~ 40 m left and right from IP4). Each will provide a 5 A ‘tube’ of electrons, confined with a solenoid magnetic field, counter-propagating concentrically around the circulating high energy hadron beams over 3 m of interaction length, see Figure 1. In order to accelerate halo depletion, the electron beam can be modulated On/Off at 35 kHz, with 200 ns rise-time. This way one can switch the e-beam on and off between trains, and target trains at random or a fixed number of turns, thereby adding a non-linear effect to the kicks given to the halo particles [6].

The degree to which the electron and hadron beams overlap as well as the electron beam profile will be measured with a new device being developed in collaboration between CERN and Cockcroft Institute [7], [8]. This so-called Beam Gas Curtain (BGC) monitor, is based on imaging beam induced gas fluorescence from a supersonic gas curtain.

Figure 1: Hollow Electron Beam around the circulating proton beam (left hand side) and schematics of the Collimation Scheme for HL-LHC (right hand side). (Image: CERN).

2.1.2 Electron Lens for Space Charge Compensation

Space charge compensation of intense ion beams (in SIS18, GSI [9], [10]) by non-neutral plasma columns is being studied within work package 16 of the ARIES project. The JRA developed and built an electron gun capable of providing electron beams currents of up to 10 A, and able to be modulated with changing longitudinal profile at a bandwidth of 10 MHz.

2.1.3 CERN Test Stand Goals

An electron beam test stand (co-founded by the ARIES project and the HiLumi LHC project in $\frac{1}{4}$ to $\frac{3}{4}$ proportions) was constructed at CERN for the following purposes:

- Acquiring operational experience with electron beams of high intensity and high space charge density (5 A in a few mm for the Hollow Electron Lens).
- Testing components for the HL-LHC Hollow Electron Lens (HEL), in particular:
 - characterizing the electron gun current emission yield as a function of cathode temperature (800 to 1000 °C) and extraction voltage (0 to 10 kV), and measuring the transverse profile of the electron beam to check uniformity and cathode material quality;
 - testing the HV modulator working at 10 kV and 5 A, 200 ns rise time and 35 kHz repetition rate;
 - testing HV power converters pulsing at 35 kHz, 200 ns rise time;
 - designing and testing the HEL control system;
 - testing the HEL collector repellers and diagnostics;
 - testing the Beam Gas Curtain diagnostics for high-density, hollow electron beams;
 - testing the Beam Position Monitor response with the available e-beam modulation.
- Testing components for space charge compensation in SIS18, in particular:
 - characterizing the electron gun current emission field and transverse profile of the electron beam;
 - testing the HV modulator.

2.2 DESCRIPTION OF THE TEST STAND

The Electron Beam Test Stand (EBTS) is being constructed using a staged approach, to commission its main components separately, and validate the measurement techniques. The present stage is shown in Figure 2, the final configuration in Figure 3.

Figure 2: Stage 1 of the EBTS as installed

Figure 3: Layout of the EBTS: it shows the electron gun (E-Gun), the diagnostic box (DBD), a sector valve, the BPM [11] and BGC [8] diagnostics for the HEL, and the Collector. (Image: CERN)

Parameter	Unit	BPM coils	All other coils
Length	[mm]	180	230
ID	[mm]	185	180
OD	[mm]	314	360
Turns, pancakes*layers		101 (17 x 6)	95 (16 x 6)
Conductor size	[mm]		13x13
Cooling bore diameter	[mm]		6.5
Max. operating current	A	600	700
Max. central B field	T	0.35	0.3

Table 1 – Solenoid coils parameters

The final stage of the ETBS has the following features:

- 8 set of solenoid NC coils, each with horizontal and vertical dipole correctors, contain and guide the electron beam.
- The so-called diagnostic box provides measurements of the transverse e-beam profile with a Pin Hole Faraday Cup and a YAG screen (see later for more details).
- A bake-out and pumping system guarantees pressures of the order of 10^{-10} mbar, when the e-gun is not heated.
- A collector chamber with passively cooled “Faraday Cup” with viewport allows measurements of the total e-beam current, and to see the light from the YAG screen.
- A pulsing device (200 ns rise time, 10 μ s pulse at 10 Hz, corresponding to a duty cycle of 10^{-4}) reduces the power onto collector and scintillator screens, and generates an e-beam as at the HEL.
- Current is measured with a transformer at the cathode power supply with 200 MHz bandwidth.

References for this type of gun and the results of similar measurements can be found in [12], [13], [14], [15].

2.2.1 Diagnostic Box

The Electron Lens Test Stand diagnostic box (see Figure 4) hosts the instrumentation able to measure electron current and transverse profile, namely a Pinhole Faraday Cup and a YAG Screen, and possibly a Langmuir probe to measure the electron temperature, electron density, and electric potential. The diagnostic box vacuum chamber (depicted in Figure 5) has several arms for the insertion of the instrumentation, a turbo-pump and a vacuum gauge. The arms have a hippodrome-like shape to minimize the space between the gun and collector solenoid (so that the magnetic field drop at the box itself is minimal) while guaranteeing that the Pinhole Faraday Cup can be swept laterally to cover the transverse size of the electron beam, and leaving enough conductance for the turbo-pump.

Figure 4: Diagnostic box showing the actuators of the Pinhole Faraday Cup and the YAG Screen, a pump and a vacuum gauge. (Image: CERN)

Figure 5: Diagnostic box vacuum chamber. (Image: CERN)

Pin-Hole Faraday Cup	Array of FDC with 0.2 mm aperture	Movements ± 30 mm in transverse direction, 0-200 mm insertion/extraction
YAG Screen	YAG:Ce crystal 40 mm diameter 2 screens, one with, one without aluminum shield	Position in or out

The CERN test stand offers the major advantage of providing diagnostics that sweep through the beam (rather than moving the beam through a fixed diagnostic set-up), a large accelerating field and a large drift magnetic field.

The fact of moving the diagnostics rather than the beam will give a more accurate measurement of the transverse beam profile, since the electron beam dynamics for such a non-relativistic beam also depends on the beam position relative to the vacuum chamber walls. For HEL applications, it is very important to accurately establish the shape of the electron beam and its dynamics (i.e. that it stays round along the whole interaction length) since the presence of a residual electric field in the center of the electron beam could perturb the circulating proton beam, especially if pulsed.

The CERN test stand also allows for a comparison between measurements with the Pinhole Faraday Cup, the YAG screen and an eventual beam gas curtain monitor.

3. E-Lens Test Stand at the E-Lens Lab of IAP

3.1 OVERVIEW

The overall layout of the test stand was taken over in a large part from the CERN design. An overview of the final test stand layout is given in Figure 6: The electron gun is integrated electrically isolated into the gun solenoid. A Faraday cup (FDC) is used to dump the electron beam. Both gun and beam dump are put on cathode potential by means of a high voltage platform. The diagnostic box between the solenoids connects the vacuum pumps. The two solenoids are magnetically connected by an additional iron casing surrounding the diagnostic box. An energy recovery system recycles the beam power within the extraction system of the gun.

Figure 6: Electrical scheme of the high voltage platform for the gun.

The test stand is set-up in different stages. In the first stage, pyrometric measurements to characterize the heating process of the cathode are performed. For this reason, the beam dump is being replaced by the pyrometer and no extraction voltage is applied. In the second stage, a Faraday cup will be

installed in the diagnostic box and first low current beam extraction experiments will be performed, for a maximum extraction voltage of 3500 V. In the final stage, the electron gun will be powered on the high voltage platform, the electron beam will be stopped in the beam dump while the energy recovery system recycles the beam power.

The first stage is still under construction, since the construction process continues to be slowed down by the limited access to work on-site due to COVID-19 regulations. The work will, nevertheless, continue beyond the end of the ARIES project, and the test stand will be completed as described before. Thereby the collaboration on electron gun activities on defined topics between Goethe University Frankfurt, GSI, RTU and CERN will continue.

The beam transport studies performed for the final stage of the test stand are presented in the following section.

3.2 BEAM DYNAMICS SIMULATIONS

The basic layout of the final test stand set-up was evaluated and improved by beam transport simulations using CST Particle Studio. According to the simulations for the given experimental restrictions in the presented test stand layout, it is not possible to fully dump a 10 A electron beam. The power deposition of the FDC is in fact limited to 27 kW, and it would be exceeded if the estimated required decelerating potential (larger than 3 kV) was to be applied. For this reason, the extracted current had to be reduced as compared to the originally planned experimental set-up. Another restriction is given by the maximum current of 500 A for the available power supply of the transfer coils located between the second solenoid and the FDC. Therefore, it became necessary to reduce the magnetic field configuration by a factor of 3 from 0.6 T to 0.2 T. Nevertheless, a further optimization of the test stand layout is planned in order to test the electron gun for full beam power in the future.

For the electron beam generation, the thermionic emission model is used. The cathode material is defined as tungsten with a heating temperature of $T=2500$ K (work function 4.54 eV). The cathode voltage is set on -18.5 kV, the grid voltage is also chosen to be -18.5 kV while the anode stays on ground potential. This configuration leads to an extracted electron current of 5.3 A. The FDC is set on a potential of -13.8 kV. That means a difference of 4.7 kV to cathode potential in order to keep the beam power deposition below 27 kW. As depicted in Figure 7 the beam is fully dumped into the FDC in this configuration.

Figure 7: Electron trajectories (top), potential distribution of test stand components (center) and on-axis magnetic field along z .

The influence of secondary electron emission from the FDC is currently under investigation. But first calculations indicate the need of an efficient secondary electron mitigation strategy for full beam power.

3.3 DESCRIPTION OF TEST STAND COMPONENTS AND FINAL SET-UP

The terminal is assembled to power the gun with maximum voltage of 35 kV (see Figure 8). The power supplies for cathode heating as well as the power modulator are also operated on this platform that is separated by an insulating transformer from ground potential. It is planned to operate all power supplies remotely in the final design stage of the test stand, therefore the remote control operation unit is under preparation and primary functions are already finished.

Figure 8: Picture of the high voltage terminal. Outside view (left) and inside view (right).

The magnetic system comprises two solenoids (see Figure 9), an iron connection of the solenoid flanges both manufactured by Scanditronix and two pancake coils for an auxiliary field to transfer the beam into the dump manufactured at Goethe University Frankfurt. The electron gun described in more detail in section 4. is immersed in the magnetic field of the first solenoid.

Figure 9: Picture of solenoid magnets for the beam transport in the test stand.

The electrical and mechanical parameters of the solenoid and the pancake coil are listed in Table 2.

	Solenoid	Pancake Coil
Max. magnetic field $B_{z,max}$ [T]	0.6	0.07
Max. current [A]	460	500
Max. voltage [V]	77	
Aperture [mm]	200	205
Length [mm]	408	16

Table 2: Electrical and mechanical parameters of solenoid and pancake coil.

The solenoid was designed for a maximum magnetic field 0.6 T while the single pancake coil produces a maximum field of 0.07 T at 500 A. An iron connection between the magnets has the double purpose of shaping the magnetic field in the region of the diagnostic box and fixing the positions of the solenoids. At the same time, it leaves enough space to introduce CF100 fittings for diagnostics etc., while keeping the distance between solenoids to a minimum in order to realize electron beam transport without losses. It was manufactured by Scanditronix and has been delivered in November 2021.

A Faraday cup (FDC) that has been designed for 27 kW beam power deposition will be used for beam dumping as well as current measurement. A hole of 1 mm at the backside of the cup gives the opportunity to analyze a small part of the decelerated electron beam. Figure 10 shows the technical drawing and a picture of the FDC. The cut-off frequency is about 600 MHz, so it will be possible to measure the time structure of the modulated electron beam with high resolution.

Figure 10: Picture (left) and technical drawing (right) of the beam dump.

A 3D model of the final test stand layout comprising the electron gun, magnets, the diagnostic box, the beam dump, and insulations is shown in Figure 11. The telescope construction at the entrance of the first solenoid is an insulation shield for the cables between the HV terminal and the electron gun.

Figure 11: Preliminary 3D model of the final test stand layout.

All parts of the test stand can be removed and realigned easily. The flexibility of the set-up enables the possibility of modifications and adaptations, when needed. Also the integration of additional beam instrumentation or sensors for hardware monitoring is possible. Finally, the whole setup is computer controlled including an autonomous instance for the electron beam handling.

3.4 TEST STAND SET-UP AT STAGE 1

The current test stand set-up comprises an HV terminal, the electron gun, two (magnetically uncoupled) solenoid magnets, a diagnostic box with integrated, small FDC and pyrometer (see Figure 12).

Figure 12: Two views of stage 1 of the test stand set-up.

In this configuration the first performance tests of the IRME-gun were executed. The results of the experiments are described in the following section.

4. Description and Tests of the IRME-Gun

4.1 OVERVIEW OF ELECTRON GUN DESIGN STAGES

The IRME electron gun was designed in order to produce a Gaussian shaped beam of 10 A current at modulation frequencies between 400 kHz and 1 MHz with 10 MHz bandwidth to create electron beam pulses resembling longitudinal bunch profiles of an ion beam. The design parameters were described in more detail in the MS53 report [16].

In order to simulate the extracted current, the software CST particle studio (CST-PS) was chosen. A gun model with Gaussian cathode but without modulation grid was provided by A. Pikin (BNL) and simulated using the codes TRAK and CST-PS. Both simulation tools delivered comparable results. For further numerical studies CST-PS was chosen since it has a unique option of implementing and simulating complex structures as the Gaussian shaped grid of the IRME-gun.

After the conceptual layout of the gun, a technical layout of a prototype gun was prepared and, subsequently, manufactured and tested. In view of the performance obtained with the prototype gun, an optimized electron gun design was elaborated, manufactured and commissioned. All these steps were accompanied by numerical simulations. The details of the different design stages will be described in the following.

4.1.1 Conceptual Electron Gun Layout

In order to generate an electron beam with Gaussian transverse current density profile, the cathode has to be shaped accordingly and the gun has to be immersed in a homogeneous magnetic field. The cathode is round with a radius of $R_c = 26.5$ mm. If an additional quadrupole field is applied right at the cathode, the transverse profile can be deformed into an elliptical shape to comply with the dimension requirements of $2\sigma_x = 35$ mm and $2\sigma_y = 20$ mm.

The Gaussian profile of the cathode is given by

$$y = y_0 + \frac{A}{w \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{2}}} e^{-\frac{2x^2}{w^2}}$$

where offset $y_0 = 0.97$ mm, width $w = 22.82$ mm, and area $A = 433.42$ mm².

The required maximum current density is in the order of 3.2 A/cm².

For the simulations in CST-PS, space-charge limited emission is chosen as tracking emission model. Physically, the space-charge limited emission can be understood as a suppression of the potential between two planar electrodes, e.g. cathode and anode, by a cloud of charges [16]. At a distance of 3 mm behind the cathode the modulation grid is placed. Besides the information on extracted maximum current, the capability of current depression by a grid and its influence on the transverse current density profile was studied. For the different grid designs simulations have been performed

in order to determine the voltage required to cut off the electron current. The final solution requires a voltage of 2500 V to 3000 V to reduce the residual electron current below 5%.

The conceptual IRME-gun layout is depicted in Figure 13 and the mechanical and electrical parameters of this conceptual design are listed in Table 3.

Figure 13 Schematic layout of the electron gun system (left) and cross section of electron gun design (right).

Electron Gun		Magnetic System	
Cathode radius R_c [mm]	26.5	Max. magnetic field of Solenoid $B_{z,max}$ [T]	0.6
Anode voltage U_A [kV]	30	Max. magnetic field of quadrupole air coil $B_{x,max}$ [T]	$0.06 \cdot B_{z,max}$
Distance cathode to anode d_{ca} [mm]	20		
Max. extracted beam current I_{max} [A]	10		
Max. grid voltage $U_{g,max}$ [kV]	3		
Grid capacity C_g [pF]	~75		
Distance cathode to grid d_{cg} [mm]	3		

Table 3 Mechanical and electrical parameters of the electron gun components.

4.1.2 Construction and Test of Prototype

Following the conceptual gun design, a prototype electron gun based on a particle volume ion source was constructed. IAP has decades of practical experience with such ion sources. The spacing and design of all parts are optimized regarding high voltage breakdowns (~ 30 kV), water cooling of electrodes, vacuum conditions, and outside isolation. The set-up of the particle source can be divided into two parts: the plasma chamber to generate an arc discharge and the extractor part. The tungsten cathode emitting the electrons and the tungsten grid were designed and manufactured to be integrated in the extractor of the original source. Cathode, grid as well as the assembled extractor part are shown in Figure 14. The design of this prototype was subsequently labeled “Tungsten Electron Emitter”, or TE² for short.

Figure 14: Pictures of tungsten cathode and grid (left). They were purchased from industry and delivered with a purity factor of 99.98%. Picture and technical drawing of the extractor part (mid and right).

The novel concept of heating a robust tungsten cathode by an arc discharge that is generated inside the plasma chamber has been investigated during an experimental campaign from July 2019 until September 2019. The goal of the experimental campaign was also to evaluate the performance of the gun concerning water cooling and vacuum conditions when the cathode is being heated up to temperatures above 2500 K which are the requirements for a necessary current density of 3.2 A/cm^2 due to the relatively high work function of pure tungsten. Furthermore, the performance of the power modulator connected to the test device was examined in a joint experimental campaign with RTU. Figure 15 shows a picture of the test set-up at Goethe University Frankfurt.

Figure 15: Second version of four-level RF inverter connected to the grid of the TE^2 prototype electron gun.

4.1.3 Design and Construction of the IRME-Gun

After the successful tests of the prototype and because of the robustness and flexibility of the set-up, it was decided to base the final design of the IRME electron gun on the TE^2 design. Since the tests had revealed some weak spots of the TE^2 design, the final design was further optimized as follows:

- The complete gun was isolated externally for integration into a solenoid.
- The grid layout was improved.
- Cooling channels were added to the anode flange.
- Two grid connections were installed with mirror symmetry.

Figure 16 shows the manufactured IRME-gun and the 3D model.

Figure 16: 3D model of the IRME-gun (left) and picture of the manufactured device (right).

The IRME-gun was assembled and tested for vacuum and water leakages in July 2021 and is now ready for operation.

4.1.4 Modulator Design

The modulator was also designed in different stages (for more details see [17], [18]). The latest version presented in Figure 17 will be used to modulate the electron gun at low current beams planned for phase 2 of the test stand set-up. The maximum output voltage is limited to 600 V but still high enough to modulate a beam of 500 mA at 3500 V.

Figure 17: Electrical circuit of the multi-level RF-inverter (left) and second version of the four-level modulator (top right) as well as its output waveform (bottom right).

The final modulator version will have 26 individual stages that are electrically separated by isolated individual power sources (see Figure 18) for a total output voltage of 3.2 kV.

Figure 18: Electrical circuit of the latest version of multilevel RF-inverter.

While this comes at the price of a more complicated design with respect to the power supply, it clearly delivers an improved curve shape of the output signal as demonstrated in Figure 19.

Figure 19: Improved output waveform of the final power modulator design (right) compared to its predecessor (left).

Unfortunately, the required semi-conductors could not be obtained due to the general supply shortage in the market. As a result, it was not possible to finish the final modulator yet.

4.2 IRME-GUN PERFORMANCE TESTS

The tungsten cathode is heated by an arc discharge that is generated within the plasma chamber of the electron gun. In a first step of the experiments, the arc discharge has to be characterized and parameters for an effective heating of the cathode while maintaining a stable and safe operation have to be defined. The vacuum condition is another important aspect which will be studied in the first phase. The heat transferred to beam tube and vacuum equipment leads to desorption and therefore degradation of ultra-high vacuum needed for the later operation of the e-lens in synchrotrons. Several strategies to mitigate vacuum problems will be tested. The measurement campaign is still ongoing at the time of writing this report, but first experimental results will be presented in the following.

4.2.1 Cathode Heating

During the experiments with the TE² prototype of the electron gun in 2019, it was found that the cathode can be heated to the required temperatures of more than 2500 K to provide a sufficient number of free electrons to generate beam currents of up to 10 A at 30 kV extraction voltage while maintaining stable operation of the source. Besides this, different methods for driving the arc discharge were studied for an effective heating of the cathode. These studies were performed for magnetic fields of up to 20 mT. But the required magnetic field to operate the gun is much higher. For this reason, in the ongoing experimental campaign the influence of the magnetic field on the arc discharge respectively the cathode heating is examined. An example of the measured temperature distribution and the evaluation is depicted in Figure 20. The temperature was measured by a pyrometer and the emissivity of tungsten was assumed to be $\epsilon = 0.1$. Therefore, the displayed temperature has to be multiplied by 1.78 to obtain the correct temperature ($T = 1403^{\circ}\text{C}$ in the presented case). The pyrometer has a spatial resolution of 1 mm^2 and it is possible to measure the deviation of the temperature across the whole cathode surface. The results will help to estimate deviations of the electron density in the extracted beam.

Figure 20: Example of the cathode temperature measured by a pyrometer (top left) and the temperature distribution (top right and bottom). The measured temperature has to be corrected and the realistic value is $T = 1403^{\circ}\text{C}$ (top, left).

Figure 21 shows the cathode temperature as a function of the magnetic field when the arc discharge directly heats the cathode.

Figure 21: Measured cathode temperature as a function of the magnetic field for a constant arc power of $p_{arc} = 525$ W.

The temperature seems to settle at one value for magnetic fields above 35 mT. In the next step, the magnetic field was set to a value on this plateau ($B_z = 39$ mT) and the arc power was varied. The temperature as a function of the arc power and the power balance are presented in Figure 22.

Figure 22: Measured cathode temperature as a function of the arc power (left) and the power balance (right).

The temperature of the cathode increases linearly with the arc power. This results in an easy and reproducible control of the temperature and therefore electron emission density. On the right hand side of Figure 22, the cathode temperature is shown as a function of the power balance between the hot filament, which drives the arc discharge, and the arc power. For an arc power above 550 W the heating mechanism seems to be supported by a secondary backflow mechanism inside the plasma chamber. Therefore, the power consumption for heating the filament is less than expected and will help to reduce the operational costs of a future e-lens.

5. Conclusion and Future Plans

Within the project duration of ARIES, the IRME-gun was designed, constructed and manufactured for application in electron lenses to compensate the space charge of bunched ion beams in hadron synchrotrons. As a reference case, the heavy ion synchrotron SIS18 at GSI has been selected. The gun is designed to deliver electron currents of 10 A at modulation frequencies between 400 kHz and 1 MHz. The tests of the electron gun couldn't be concluded within the project period as delays incurred due to the COVID-19 regulations and the construction of the second test stand but are still ongoing.

The gun performance is currently examined at the test stand at the IAP of Goethe University Frankfurt. It will provide virtual access for the collaborators of WP16. The set-up undergoes modifications according to the three planned project phases. Within the first phase, the heating procedure as well as the heat transfer and the thermal conduction are evaluated carefully; in addition, the vacuum behavior of the gun is studied. First experimental results were presented in this report. Within the second phase it is planned to test grid modulation of the beam created by the IRME-gun using the prototype modulator developed at Riga Technical University with a maximum electron beam power of about 7 kW. This limit is given by a dedicated Faraday cup with a base frequency of about 650 MHz to study the modulated density in the extracted and transported electron beam. Within phase three the electron gun and the final stage of the test stand will be conditioned by increasing the electron beam power step by step. Furthermore, a performance evaluation and beam dynamics studies are planned at beam powers of 100 kW. In the future, the test stand will be further upgraded in order to prove the main components of an electron lens for space charge compensation, including the IRME-gun, at full beam power of 300 kW.

Previously, the test stand at CERN was constructed to test the IRME-gun as well as the gun for the Hollow Electron Lens for the HL-LHC. The CERN test stand is now running in parallel to the one at IAP. It provides unique diagnostics to analyze the electron beam and its spatial structure. Joint research activities and scientific exchange of Goethe University Frankfurt, Riga Technical University, CERN, and GSI on the development of major components of electron lenses as well as simulation tools were established and will be continued beyond the end of ARIES.

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Annex: Glossary

Acronym	Definition
BGC	Beam Gas Curtain
BPM	Beam Position Monitor
EBTS	Electron Beam Test Stand
FDC	Faraday Cup
HEL	Hollow Electron Lens
HL-LHC	High-Luminosity Large Hadron Collider
HV	High Voltage
IRME	Intense, RF Modulated Electron Beams (name of WP)
NC	Normal Conducting
SC	Space Charge
TE ²	Tungsten Electron Emitter (prototype electron gun design)
YAG	Yttrium Aluminum Garnet